

Supplementary Materials –Tables S1-S4

Table S1. Comparison of clusters with higher social support and lower social support in 2018

Variables	Cluster 1 - Higher Social Support n = 18,345	Cluster 2 – Lower Social Support n = 10,833	p – value, Cramer’s V
Parental Role in Emotional Support	Yes (100.0%)	No (52.8%)	p < 0.01 (Cramer’s V = 0.64)
Teacher relationship satisfaction	Satisfied/Totally satisfied (100.0%)	Not at all satisfied/ Not satisfied (73.8%)	p < 0.01 (Cramer’s V = 0.80)
Sex	Females (51.4%)	Males (52.4%)	p < 0.01 (Cramer’s V = 0.05)

Table S2. Comparison of clusters with higher social support and lower social support in 2022

Variables	Cluster 1 - Higher Social Support n = 19, 534	Cluster 2 – Lower Social Support n = 9,842	p – value, Cramer’s V
Parental Role in Emotional Support	Yes (100.0%)	No (54.0%)	p < 0.01 (Cramer’s V = 0.66)
Teacher relationship satisfaction	Satisfied/Totally satisfied (100.0%)	Not at all satisfied/ Not satisfied (71.7%)	p < 0.01 (Cramer’s V = 0.79)
Sex	Males (50.3%)	Males (51.1%)	p = 0.20 (Cramer’s V = 0.01)

Table S3. Calculations of the cluster - based prevalence estimates

Year	Outcome	Cluster 1 n/N (%)	Cluster 2 n/N (%)
2018	Depression	7,623/18,345 (41.6)	5,499/10,833 (50.8)
2018	Anxiety	7,053/18,345 (38.4)	4,710/10,833 (43.5)
2022	Depression	9,403/19,534 (48.1)	5,771/9,842 (58.6)
2022	Anxiety	9,027/19,534 (46.2)	5,535/9,842 (56.2)

Note: Prevalence (%) was calculated as the number of Spanish adolescents reporting the condition divided by the total number of adolescents within each cluster.

Table S4. Summary of missing data across study variables in the PISA 2018 and 2022 datasets

2018			
Variable	Missing (n)	Non-missing (n)	% Missing
Depression	6,304	29,639	17.5
Anxiety	6,304	29,639	17.5
Difficulty sleeping	6,304	29,639	17.5
Parental role in emotional support	6,765	29,178	18.8
Satisfaction with teacher relationships	6,363	29,580	17.7
2022			
Depression	1,352	29,448	4.3
Anxiety	1,352	29,448	4.3
Difficulty sleeping	1,352	29,448	4.3
Parental role in emotional support	1,424	29,376	4.6
Satisfaction with teacher relationships	1,369	29,431	4.4
Experience of mood swings	1,045	29,755	3.3
Nervous or anxious feelings without a digital device	946	29,854	3.0

Note: The sex variable was not included in the Table because it contained no missing data.